

DESIGNING THE STRUCTURE OF A HYBRID CONFERENCE

Joni Mok (aursticflute@gmail.com)
University of Oslo, Oslo, Norway.

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the conceptual and technical setups of the recent Rhythm, Production and Perception Workshop (RPPW) 2021 hybrid conference. For this conference, there were adaptations to accommodate the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic which has prevailed since 2020. Many academic conferences were cancelled because of logistical uncertainties and this one had to be redesigned. Such conditions challenge us to think beyond how we used to live. A hybrid conference can keep academic events and academics connected at a distance but they do alter the way interactions occur. During the 4-day RPPW conference, 300 attendees from more than 25 nations were helped to interact and to overcome time-zone differences. The conference consisted of presentations, live Q& A sessions, poster sessions, keynotes and 3 concerts. The main challenges were the (1)conference scheduling and (2)participation methods. The spatial and temporal conditions of a physical conference needed to be rethought in an intuitive way such that participants had as clear an idea of the structure of the event as possible. This demonstration invites further discussion on the potential of audiovisual communication and its socio-technical contribution to enriching human knowledge exchange, flexibility and hybrid social interaction.

1. INTRODUCTION

A hybrid conference is a type of organized conference that combines both physical and digital participation experiences. A hybrid conference is delivered as usual with a portion of attendees physically present and the other portion viewing and participating remotely. The underlying principle of a hybrid conference is for both digital and physical participants to have identical experiences in terms of quality, interaction, viewing and access.

Hybrid conferences, write Roos et al. [6] “are extremely powerful and bring additional value to many people and may even reduce the gap between high- and low-educated
Copyright: © 2021 the Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

regions. But virtual meetings are also inherently impoverishing as they miss the extra dimension of the direct human-to-human interaction.” Sá et al. [7] refer to such conferences as pure-virtual: which “includes a set of external locations linked by a virtual network of the central conference. Participants can remotely join the event from any part of the world” [7].

In 2021, the COVID crisis meant that a physical conference was too risky: chiefly the hazard of unplanned cancellations. To avoid undesirable postponements or cancellations, the 18th Rhythm Production and Perception Workshop (RPPW 2021) embraced a hybrid format for hosting this year’s conference. It was organized by the RITMO Centre for Interdisciplinary Studies in Rhythm, Time and Motion (RITMO) and a collaboration with the Music, Communication and Technology masters (MCT) at the University of Oslo (UiO). It was a medium-sized 4-day conference with approximately 300 on-and-off attendees joining from 25 nations.

To ensure participants have as clear an idea of the structure of the event as possible, the RPPW 2021 designed a website that serves as an information hub where participants can find all the information required without looking up particular links from their email inbox. The website also showed how the conference is structured so that the attendees who were not in the same time zone in Norway (where the conference was based) can also adjust the conference programme to their own time zones. Then, the RPPW 2021 tackled the following design goals in this project:

- Conference Scheduling
- Participation methods

2. CONCEPTUAL PLANNING

2.1 Software and scheduling

Conference attendees came from Australia, North America and Europe. The scheduling of the 4-day workshop programme was intricate in the sense that some participants joined the conferences in their nighttime and for some, in the early morning. To accommodate this situation, we decided to begin the conference in the

afternoon time in the host city (Oslo). We compacted the programmes into a 6-hour daily plan with 15 minutes break between sections. Figure 1 below shows an overview of the conference scheduling structure and used communication channels.

Figure 1. Overview of the conference schedule and communication channels.

The 4-day conference had 40 main presentations and 60 posters. The main presentations ran on a Zoom Webinar. This was because a Zoom Webinar is particularly designed for large audiences or events that are open to the public. In addition, it allows attendees to have Q & A sessions in a more organized manner while Zoom Meeting is ideal for hosting smaller group meetings. Its “breakout room” function fits well for the poster sessions. The 60 posters were distributed across the 4-day programme. Each poster presenter was assigned to a Zoom room. Based on attendees’ interest, the attendees were sent to the breakout Zoom room for their chosen poster.

Figure 2. Overview of the hybrid conference communication channel structure.

2.2 Hybrid Social Interaction

Figure 3 shows the relations between physical/digital attendees and communication channels. The organization design focused on the four subjects as listed below:

- Physical attendance: being in the room (Oslo)

- Digital attendance: remote room
- Monitoring-response: looking in Slack
- Correspondence: the RPPW website and Slack

Figure 3. Overview of relations between attendees and communication channels.

Before making decisions on how to organize the hybrid social interaction. Some tools for virtual socialization were explored. It was known that other conferences were using apps such as Gathertown and Glimpse. In order to assess whether it was worth using those apps for socialization, some explorative, unstructured user interviews were conducted with conference-goers in other existing online conferences such as in the Future Directions of Music Cognition [2] and Design as Common Good [1]. Four personas were created and were based on the user interviews with the researchers in the above-mentioned conferences. Discovering the common patterns in the 4 personas, we learned that researchers found having to try so many apps in one conference to be rather distracting. Some expressed their experiences with the virtual socializations app and found the idea was more like a speed-dating app than a conference networking app.

We have decided to use Slack as our main communication channel, so as to avoid over-complication. Being inspired by the explorative interviews, we designed a website for information purposes. Its intention was to lessen researchers’ attention span spent on finding the “right email” in their email inbox. But the purpose of the website was to provide all information that a conference participant might need, such as the Zoom link to relevant topics and tags to allow for a quick search for relevance.

3. TECHNICAL SET-UP

To ensure participants could interact with other attendees at time of their preference, we designed our own RPPW 2021 website [5]. It allows attendees to find out the

programmes and the relevant information. A Slack platform was set up for real-time communication between organizers and attendees in different locations. In the Slack medium, we created different channels such as #presentation_theme_1, #keynote_1 and so on. This encouraged participants to discuss the topics. In every presentation, we provided longer time for live Q&A sessions. The use of Slack allows attendees to keep the discussion going even after the presentation.

Figure 4. Slack channels for specific topics discussions.

The idea of running a hybrid conference and not purely a virtual one was due to our wish for participants in the local area to be able to engage in-person. With consideration to both physical and digital attendees in mind, we opened a special Zoom room allowed anyone to join who was either physically in the Cafeteria at RITMO or from anywhere digitally. The technical setup was simple. We connected a computer to the AV technologies that were available in the Cafeteria.

Figure 5. This shows how the physical setting (cafeteria) and virtual setting were connected.

There were three live-streaming performances and each had separate different technical challenges. 1) A performance between a human dancer and a robot in two locations, 2) a telematic performance in three locations and 3) a Norwegian folk music performance. Despite the

fact that they were different, the core idea was “live-streaming”. In this regard, figure 6 shows the setup in our local concert room 1. The key tool was Open Broadcaster Software (OBS) to run live-streaming concerts. This tool allows video recording, connecting to any live-streaming or video conferencing platforms, in this case, it was both Youtube and Zoom.

Figure 6. This shows the audiovisual set-up for streaming in concert room 1.

4. POST-CONFERENCE SURVEY KEY FINDINGS

The conference ended with a follow-up survey which allowed quantitative and qualitative responses. Sixty-five survey participants left their feedback about the overall conference experience. The main tenor of the respondents was positive. Typical was this: “the content and the interaction were engaging; the conference was well-organized”. Many expressed that using just one communication channel i.e. Slack has maximized the overall social engagement. We have again proved that the German catchphrase “Weniger ist mehr (English: Less is more)” works, in this case in the planning of a hybrid conference context.

From the quantitative responses, 47.4% and 24.6% out of 57 respondents found that the social and technological factors were the most important as a conference format. The aspect of in-person social interaction was most preferable ahead of technology and others concerns. This resonates with what Roos et al. [6] write “We can’t just suddenly make a conference be online”. The social aspect is therefore crucial in innovation and technological advancement.

Figure 7. One of the quantitative survey responses we received from participants.

5. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The conceptual planning for the RPPW 2021 was inspired by the NIME [3] and ISMIR [9] conferences. What made RPPW 2021 different from the previous virtual conferences was that we had physical attendees. In a sense, the conference was not a conversion of a real one to a virtual one, but the grafting of a real conference than to a virtual one.

The conference scheduling was carefully tailored with different attendees from around the world in mind. We needed to be mindful of the sleeping-waking hours' routines of the participants. The overall feedback of users was positive but the scheduling could be done even better, specifically, some participants felt the breaks were too short and the programme too intense. A 4-day conference without sufficient break in between the different sections could be draining. The live-streaming setups for the three performances went smoothly. Certainly, the audio-visual synchronisation requires further improvement in terms of latency. However, the biggest challenge to this issue was that there was no guarantee of seamless live-streaming to every attendees' personal computer. Some might connect with the ethernet and some might connect with the Wi-Fi. This is an ongoing challenge for network development. On the other hand, the social interaction in a hybrid format worked well with just one communication channel, such as Slack, without forcing users to use other socialization tools online. The idea of having everything in one place ended up being more interactive and engaging for most participants. It was also more intuitively satisfying.

Finally, running a hybrid conference requires careful planning and organization. It is important to stay true to the principle of providing the highest level of interaction quality to both the physical and digital participants. "Prior to 2020, there has been resistance to moving these events online because of the perception that the value of conferences cannot be cultivated online" [4]. As such, the technological setup requires testing, flawlessness and being 'ready-to-go whilst also delivering the content of

the conference to attendees in the most engaging way possible.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] Design as Common Good. (2021). <https://designascommongood.ch/>
- [2] Future Directions of Music Cognition. (2021). <http://org.osu.edu/mascats/>
- [3] Granieri, N. (2020). Organizing an Online Conference. *Medium*.
- [4] Niner, H. J., & Wassermann, S. N. (2021). Better for Whom? Leveling the Injustices of International Conferences by Moving Online. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8, 146.
- [5] RPPW. (2021). <https://rppw2021.org/>.
- [6] Roos, G., Oláh, J., Ingle, R., Kobayashi, R., & Feldt, M. (2020). Online conferences—Towards a new (virtual) reality. *Computational and Theoretical Chemistry*, 1189, 112975.
- [7] Sá, M. J., Ferreira, C. M., & Serpa, S. (2019). Virtual and face-to-face academic conferences: comparison and potentials. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 9(2), 35-35.
- [8] The University of Oslo. (2021). Manual for Forsamlingssalen's streaming system setup. <https://www.uio.no/ritmo/english/research/labs/fourms/handbook/forsamlingssalen/index.html>
- [9] Upham, F., Hopkins, E. et al. (2020). ISMIR 2020 Final Report.

7. PEOPLE

The MCT team members who took part in the project planning: Joni Mok, Pedro Lucas, Stephen Gardener, Rayam Soeiro. And the RITMO team.